

Investigation on academic remote sensing education across the globe: the case of Nigeria

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Abstract—In the framework of an action for the regional Aerospace Industry Cluster in Lombardy, Italy, our research group is conducting a review of higher education activities in aerospace and remote sensing. Analysing various models and approaches to the matter that can be found in different places should help finding the “locally best” approach to education in a particularly promising field, starting from a global perspective. In this paper, one of a series, we focussed on Nigeria. We thus report our main findings about the current state of things and time evolution of remote sensing in Nigerian universities, with focus on identifying high-impact institutions and key drivers of educational and research productivity nationally. With previous similar studies already carried out at global, European and Italian national levels, this work brings needful details into this study from a country and region previously unconsidered.

Index Terms—Remote sensing, Earth observation, Space education, educational institutions, Nigeria, Africa

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the burgeoning global aerospace and remote sensing ecosystem, the academia plays the role of ensuring consistent supply of competent talents and timely new knowledge to drive continuous innovation. With increasing academic and industry focus on education and research in this domain in recent years, there has been development of new solutions applicable across vertical domains including national security, climate change modeling, resource management, disaster management, precision agriculture, health risks mapping, governance, among others. It thus becomes needful to investigate the state and progress of remote sensing education in academic institutions globally, zooming locally into regional hubs for more detailed observations.

A global investigation on the state of remote sensing education was done in [1], with supporting initial investigations focusing on Europe in [2] and Italy in [3]. As envisaged in previous publications, more case studies were desirable on single relevant countries to make the investigation more significant and the emerging picture more complete. This paper brings indeed new perspectives into this study by focusing on Nigeria - a major player in the African region.

The Nigerian National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) was indeed established in May, 1999 as part of the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology to

coordinate and implement the Nigerian space program [4]. It currently has 5 space missions under management; 3 for Earth observation, one for educational purpose, and the other for communication. The space policy of the country focuses on capacity building in space technologies, international cooperations, private sector participation and support for universities and other academic institutions in space related research and development projects. These objectives are driven through major activity centres scattered nationwide, majorly within university facilities [5] [6].

Higher education on space-related topics developed accordingly, with several institutions nationwide contributing to the buildup of suitable professional knowledge intended to fuel the “space development” of the country.

This paper offers a general review of remote sensing education in Nigerian universities, presenting the state of things and the key drivers of remote sensing education across the 12 Nigerian universities most relevant to the study. The next chapter discusses the approach for selecting these universities as the statistical sample for this work. In Chapter 3, the analysis which has been carried out on each sample university is discussed. Chapter 4 presents the findings from our analysis of the statistical sample. Chapter 5 focuses on the evolution in time of research productivity in the remote sensing domain in Nigeria. In Chapter 6, some conclusions are drawn to close the paper.

II. THE STATISTICAL SAMPLE

As retrieved from the website of the National Universities commission of Nigeria (NUC), an open source database of all accredited universities operating in Nigeria, the country possesses about 162 fully accredited universities with 41 owned by the federal government, 47 by state (regional) government, and 74 privately owned, spread across the entire country. For the purpose of collecting relevant data for this work, geocoordinates of these universities were obtained, and then validated using Google Earth as a verification source.

Taking a look at the spatial distribution of these Universities as presented in figure 4, it can be noted a north-south disparity in density of universities. There are lots of factors that could have contributed to this disparity. One of such is that the southern region was the first to be exposed to western education in Nigeria, and this is where European educational models were initially imported. Other subtle contributions include the location of the crude oil producing areas and the current economic capital of the country, Lagos, being located in the southern region of the country [7].

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In furtherance, taking a cue from previous similar works done at global level in [1] and European level in [2], scientific production was used as proxy to educational activities and relevant institutional affiliations. This helps to reduce the volume of work done by focusing the research on universities that have been most productive in the field of remote sensing.

A paper search was made on Scopus [8] database for the keywords “Remote sensing”, “Aerospace” and “Earth Observation”, with entries considered from 1960 - the year Nigeria obtained independence.

Scopus had been selected for the same purpose in the previous assessments done in [1] and [2], thus it was considered sufficient for the procedure of this work. A selection was made based on affiliation and the results are presented in the graphs and charts contained in the work. The resulting publication affiliation data contained Nigerian institutions and other institutions across the world with research publications focused on Nigeria, within our thematic scope. Consequently, the data had to be cleaned to retain only universities located in Nigeria.

After filtering geographically, the top-ranked universities with publications relating to each focus keyword were obtained and presented in figures 1, 2 and 3. Looking at these publication rankings obtained, it can be sorted a group of 12 universities each of which appears among the top 7 in at least one of the three rankings. These twelve (12) universities were selected as our statistical sample. A spatial distribution of our statistical sample is presented in figure 5, reflecting somehow the higher concentration of educational institutions in South-Western Nigeria.

Fig. 1. Rank of Nigerian Universities found on Scopus for the keyword “Earth observation”

III. THE ANALYSIS

Once the 12 focus universities had been selected, we searched through their websites to retrieve information about educational activities relating to our focus keywords. Resulting from the fact that undergraduate courses are quite generic and normally do not provide enough specialization and inclination towards research activities, this search was limited to masters degree level programmes.

Fig. 2. Rank of Nigerian Universities found on Scopus for the keyword “Remote Sensing”

Fig. 3. Rank of Nigerian Universities found on Scopus for the keyword “Aerospace”

One thing that became immediately clear was the dichotomy between *aerospace*-related course tracks, and those related to *remote sensing* and *Earth observation*. This, as observed also in [1], is due to rationale of *aerospace*-focused courses being to shape engineers with capabilities for hardware design in space mission actualization and management. *Earth observation* and *remote sensing*, on the other hand, are incorporated as tools in diverse range of applications that require space data processing. Most courses incorporating them are found within the sciences faculties - environmental, physical and Earth sciences.

IV. THE FINDINGS

In Nigeria, there a a strong relationship between educational activities, research productivity and strength of supporting affiliate centres present within the University premises. This is expected from the general strategy of designing partnerships between universities and affiliate centres such that both parties leverage each others’ strength in achieving *a priori*-defined strategic objectives. Thus, the centres have been established

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of Nigerian Universities

within the university premises to rely on the educational, human resources and other institutional infrastructures of the universities in achieving their goals, while they (the centres) also provide resources to advance learning activities in the universities.

In the highlight below, the reader will find for each university in our statistical sample an overview of target courses related master degree programs, relevant centres present in the University, and in some cases research groups.

A. Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU)

This university, being one of the largest in Nigeria, offers about 10 courses related to our thematic focus. About 7 these courses are offered through affiliated institutes collaborating with the University. First of such institutes is the Regional centre for Training in Aerospace Surveys (RECTAS); a Geoinformatics training, research, consultancy and advisory centre established in 1972 under the coverage of the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA). This institute, in addition to its other activities, offers professional and executive masters programs through the university in courses including:

Geographic Information Science (GIS), Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing and Geo-information Production and Management (Cartography). Some of the courses taught within these programs include: fundamentals of GIS, Fundamentals of remote sensing, fundamentals of cartography, GIS in environmental management, GIS in Meteorology and climate change, spatial data bases analysis, data acquisition and mapping, digital cartographic production and web mapping, and Digital image processing [9].

The Institute of Environment and ecological studies (IEES) is a unit of the university which provides a research-based master's degree course in Environmental control and management. Under this institute is the Space Applications and Environmental Science Laboratory (SPAEL) - a research group with specific focus on actualizing sustainable development in the society through Remote sensing, GIS, climate change, Environmental protection etc.[10].

Another institute of note hosted within OAU is the African regional centre for space science and technology - English (ARCSTE-E), an initiative of NASRDA in affiliation with the United Nations Office of Outer Space Affairs (UNO-OSA).

Fig. 5. Spatial spread of 12 universities selected as statistical sample for this study.

This centre leverages the resources of this university to fulfil its focus on capacity building. It offers master's degree programs in Satellite Communication (SATCOM), Satellite Meteorology (SATMET), Remote Sensing/Geo Information System (RS/GIS), Basic Space and Atmospheric Science (BSAS). This particular collaboration also involves the Federal University of Technology, Akure, as discussed in IV-B below[11].

B. Federal University of Technology, Akure. (FUTA)

This University on the 3rd of June, 2017 launched a satellite named Nigeria Edusat 1, built proprietarily in conjunction with NASRDA and the Japanese Birds-1 program. This highlights the level of involvement this university displays in space related educational activities, particularly space hardware engineering education. The satellite mission is for Earth observation and technology display to support capacity development for the space industry in Nigeria.

Major educational tracks supporting the University's space and satellites initiatives include, among others, programs offered through the collaboration with OAU and ARCSSTEE already highlighted in IV-A above. The programs are offered through the departments of Physics, Meteorology and Remote Sensing and GIS, and the Centre for Space Research and Applications (CESRA) of the university. In the Satellite communications and Basic space physics tracks, courses offered include: Basic Spacecraft Design and Launch, Satellite Communication Technology, Antenna Systems Design and Theory, Applications and Trends in Satellites Communication, Satellite Imagery, and Radio Frequency (RF) and Microwave systems.

The satellite meteorology track focuses on studying the atmosphere through remote sensing and offers courses including Principles of Radar Technology, Radar in Satellite Meteorology, Climate Systems Modelling, among others. The Remote sensing and GIS track focuses on analysis of geospatial data and provides courses including Geostatistical analysis, Emergency management, Defense and Intelligence applications, Business applications of GIS, among others.[12]

Other space related MSc courses offered by this University include Applied Geophysics, Applied Geology (with Remote sensing option), Meteorology, Remote Sensing and Geoscience Information Systems, Land Management, and Urban and Regional Planning, all implicitly or explicitly remote sensing related.

In addition to CESRA, this University collaborates with the Regional Centre for Training in Aerospace Surveys (RECTAS), West African Centre on Climate Change and Adapted Land Use (WASCAL) and Cooperative Information Network (COPINE)- an initiative of NASRDA actively involved in space application processing and analysis.

Worth mentioning also is the FUTA space club; a students driven initiative that supports collaboration and co-creation among students with interest and focus in space technology and its applications.

C. University of Lagos

The University of Lagos provides master level degree programmes including Surveying and Geoinformatics, Geography and Planning (with Remote sensing option), Geology, Geophysics, and Urban and Regional Planning. Housed within this University is the centre for Environmental Human Resources Development which is a subsidiary of the University with learning and research objectives including geospatial analysis of disaster areas, climate science, public health impacts and interventions, urban areas planning, among others. In powering these objectives, the institute runs well-equipped laboratories for cartography, remote sensing and GIS. As a leading ESRI institution-licensed centre in Africa, multiple ArcGIS software extension licences are available to the University community, enabling the possibility of increased learning and research in the field of remote sensing.

Also collaborating with this University is the Centre for Space Transport and Propulsion (CSTP) - an activity centre of NASRDA that focuses on indigenous capability for launching of satellites and aerospace engineering.

Some notable Remote Sensing related research groups in this University are: Geospatial and Environmental information research group, Lagos Urban Research Group and Land Administration and Spatial Data Infrastructure for Disaster Management and Resilience Research Group.

D. Federal University of Technology, Minna (FUT Minna)

This university runs master programmes in Geotechnical Engineering, Urban and Regional Planning, Surveying and Geoinformatics (with track options in geodesy, Photogrammetry, remote sensing, hydrography and geoinformatics), Geography (with Applied Meteorology, Remote Sensing Application and Environmental Management options), Sustainable Urban Development and Urban Ecology.

With regards to space applications related learning and research institutes located in this University, there exists a Centre for human settlement and urban development (CHSUD) which undertakes training and research in human settlements planning, urban governance and urban development.

This university collaborates with the Niger State Geographic Information System (NIGIS), established to effectively coordinate and enhance land use administration and documentation process, as well as leverage on same to improve revenue generation within the state that hosts this University. This can be highlighted as a constructive collaboration between this University and its host state in the area of space application for social good.

Other notable centres in collaboration with this university include WASCAL, RECTAS (see definitions in subch. IV-B), and an activity centre of NARSDA.

E. Nnamdi Azikwe University

Notable space applications master's degree programmes provided by this University include Surveying and Geoinformatics, Geography and Meteorology, and Geological Sciences. It collaborates with the Centre for Spaces Research and Applications (CESRA), and centre for Basic Space Science and Astronomy (CBSSA), both through NASRDA.

F. University of Ilorin

This University provides MSc courses in Geographic information studies and Geology. Regarding space applications related collaborations, there is the centre for Space Transport and Propulsion (CSTP) - an activity centre of NARSDA that focuses on indigenous capability for launching of satellites and aerospace engineering. The presence of this centre in this university positively correlates with the university's top ranking in terms research productivity for the "Aerospace" keyword as shown in fig. 3.

This university also collaborates with Centre for Space Research and Applications (CESRA).

G. University of Ibadan

Master's degree programmes offered by this University include Geotechnical Engineering, Mineral Exploration (with options in: Geochemistry, Economic/Mining Geology, Geophysics), Urban and Regional Planning and a professional master programme in Geographical information systems (GIS). One instance of GIS and Spatial data processing application found outside the usual environmental and earth sciences faculty in this University is the course in Earthquake engineering taught in the first year of the MSc in Structural and Materials Engineering offered by the Civil Engineering department of the University. This course incorporates spatial data and GIS in environmental risk management application.

This university collaborates with CSTP - a NASRDA powered aerospace engineering capacity building hub, the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) - with application of spatial data and GIS technology in planning and implementation of agricultural research activities, and other collaborative subsidiaries of NARSDA.

H. University of Benin, Nigeria (UNIBEN)

This university provides master's degree programmes in Geotechnical engineering, Water resources and environment

health engineering, Engineering Geology, Environmental Geoscience, Geoinformatics, and Urban and regional planning. A notable space related research centre in this university is the National centre for Energy and Environment. This centre engages and facilitates *avant-garde* research and development initiative across disciplinary boundaries in Bioenergy production and Environmental Management. It hosts a GIS laboratory and a weather station, both to support its strategic goals.[13]

NASRDA also collaborates with this University through its Centre for Basic Space Science and Astronomy (CBSSA).

I. University of Nigeria, Nsukka

This university offers MSc courses in Environmental Management and Control, Disaster Risk Management, Urban and Regional Planning, Geoinformatics and Surveying and Geology.

Earth observation related research groups in this University include the Geophysics/Atmospheric Physics and Space research group - based in the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the university and focused on research/studies of Sun-Earth interaction, investigating phenomena of solid earth geophysics, and their relation to ionospheric geophysics.

In the department of Geoinformatics and Surveying of the University, there exists a Marine and Coastal studies research group, which focuses on researching solutions to problems in the field of Marine and Oceanographic activities in Nigeria. Also in this department is the Geodesy and Navigation Group which focuses on development of geodetic products to support surveying and mapping, navigation, and geo-scientific research. The Geospatial Analysis and GIS Research Group in the same department focuses on the application of GIS-based algorithms for spatial data processing to better understand environmental phenomena.[14]

Notable learning and research centres within the thematic focus of this work present in this University include CESRA, centre for Disaster Risk Management and Development Studies (CDRMDS), Centre for Environmental Management and Control, and NARSDA - through its activity centre CBSSA.

J. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

In its Geography department, this university offers MSc courses in Disaster management, Environmental management, Remote sensing and GIS, and Geography. M.Sc programmes available outside the Geography department include Geology and Geomatics.

The Centre for Spatial Information Science in this university works to support policy making towards sustainable urbanisation through its cutting edge research activities. Other institutes with presence in this university are Centre for Disaster Risk Management and Development Studies, NCRS, Nigerian Airforce and the Nigeria Defence Academy (NDA).

K. Delta State University, Abraka

This University offers a master's degree course in Geology and has a collaboration with NASRDA through its activity centre, CBSSA.

L. Ebonyi State University

This university offers MSc courses Geology and exploration, and Geophysics. Remote sensing related facilities in this University include the Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Laboratory (UAVL), and NASRDA's CBSSA.

V. SUCCESSIVE EVOLUTION

Fig. 6. Time evolution of number the of publications for the keywords: “Aerospace”, “Earth Observation” and “Remote sensing” by Nigerian Universities from 1988 to 2017

Taking a look the time series of the publications records available obtained for each keyword search in the procedure of this work, as can be seen in fig 6, the level of research productivity within the academic Remote sensing community in Nigeria is on the rise. scientific activity in remote sensing saw the starting of a significant growth trend in Nigeria between 2006-2010. Since the NARSDA was established in 1999, it is highly probable that educational and research activities had began to improve from that time, with a ripple effect on research productivity emerging after a few years, thus 2006 - 2010. From the findings of this work, 11 out of the 12 universities in our statistical sample are in direct collaboration with NASRDA. This highlights the effect of the space agency in enabling research initiatives in Nigerian universities, thus pointing to NASRDA as a key driver to the growing trend seen in figure 6.

Another probable contribution to this growth is the a global growth in number of publications within the remote sensing academic domain as reported in [1], which impact Nigeria to some extent like any other country, as an effect of increased pressure to publish and increased ease of online publication.

VI. CONCLUSION

It can be seen that research productivity in the Remote sensing domain is growing in Nigerian universities. The findings of our survey work highlight the role of NASRDA, and consequently the National space program, to this growth. Also, it can be seen that collaborations between Universities and external learning/research centres provide mutually beneficial relationships to improve remote sensing education in Nigeria.

However, one limitation of our approach is that it only points to explicit contributions to remote sensing education

using the keywords: “Earth Observation”, “Remote sensing” and “Aerospace Engineering”. Other implicit contributions, especially in the area of Aerospace engineering include teaching and research activities in Robotics, Mechanical engineering, Electronic Engineering, among others. There are also applications of GIS in Civil engineering which have not been covered in this report due to lack of referenceable evidences. As a consequence, we might have oversimplified the scope and drivers of remote sensing education in Nigeria, yet we believe this is a possible way to start reasoning on the mechanisms.

Another limitation of our approach is that it doesn’t use data on number of students currently or previously enrolled in each of the tracks that have been analyzed, because such data is quite difficult to obtain, especially countrywide. These additional elements would be useful in educational impact assessment and contributions to local industry needs.

Due to complexity and multidisciplinary of remote sensing, and the limitations stated above, this paper will rather not posit completeness. Instead, this paper offers a trigger to initiate conversations on Remote sensing education in Nigeria, and contribute to the global level study done in [1]. As for the previous papers in this series, the authors are available to discuss the results presented, and open to relevant inputs from interested parties and stakeholders.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Dell’Acqua and G. Siciliano, “Technical Education on Aerospace and Remote Sensing: A brief global overview,” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 8–14, 2018.
- [2] F. Dell’Acqua and L. Pasca, “Technical Education in the European University System on Aerospace and Remote Sensing: A year 2013 review [Education],” *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 29–33, Mar. 2014, ISSN: 2473-2397.
- [3] F. Dell’Acqua, “Technical education on aerospace and remote sensing in the Italian university system; A brief overview,” in *2014 IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Jul. 2014, pp. 4524–4527.
- [4] R. A. Boroffice, “The Nigerian space programme: an update,” *African Skies*, vol. 12, p. 40, 2008.
- [5] *National Space Research and Development Agency*, Accessed on 2018-06-26. [Online]. Available: <http://nasrda.gov.ng/en/>.
- [6] H. O. Aro and L. Adetoro, “Nigeria Space Programs,” 2011.
- [7] V. A. Isumonah and F. O. Egwaikhide, “Federal presence in higher institutions in nigeria and the north/south dichotomy,” *Regional & Federal Studies*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 169–188, 2013.

- [8] *Scopus claims being the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com>.
- [9] *Regional Centre for Training in Aerospace Surveys (RECTAS), Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: <http://www.rectas.org>.
- [10] *Space Applications and Environmental Science Laboratory (SPAEL), Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: <http://www.spaeloau.org>.
- [11] *African Regional Centre for Space Science and Technology - English, Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: <http://arcsstee.org.ng/index.php/divisions/post-graduate-programme>.
- [12] *African regional centre for space science and technology - English (ARCSTE-E) - M.Sc curriculum*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: http://arcsstee.org.ng/download/MASTERS_CURRICULUM.pdf.
- [13] *The National Centre for Energy and Environment(NCEE) - University of Benin, Nigeria*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: <http://ncee.org.ng>.
- [14] *Research groups, University of Nigeria, Nsukka*, Accessed on 2018-06-21. [Online]. Available: <http://www.unn.edu.ng/research-groups>.